

**THE IMPACT OF GIRL-CHILD EDUCATION ON COMMUNITY
DEVELOPMENT IN ESSIEN UDIM LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF AKWA
IBOM STATE, NIGERIA**

Aniekan Nya

Department of Sociology and Anthropology
University of Uyo, Uyo

ABSTRACT

This study was carried out to examine The Impact of girl-child education on Community Development in Essien Udim Local Government Area. Many Girls of secondary school ages (13-8 years old) are not in schools. Despite the free education programme by the State Government, these attitudes affect the developmental processes of the communities. Functionalism and Social Learning theories were adopted for theoretical framework. Data for the study were generated from the survey method, using a systematic random sampling technique which covered 224 (112 males, 112 females) respondents in the 7 clans of Essien Udim Local Government Areas. Twenty-one itemised structured questionnaires were administered and responses were tabulated and analysed using the chi-square statical technique. The result of the findings shows that there is a significant relationship between Girl-Child's education and Community Development, there is a significant relationship between Girl-Child's education and women's participation in politics, and Sociocultural factors account for the low level of Girl-Child enrollment in schools. However, it was discovered that girls' stubbornness, promiscuous lifestyle which led to early marriage and unwanted pregnancy and lack of interest in education the problem with the Girl-child in Essien Udim. The researcher recommended that society should stop discrimination against the girl-child in the provision of education, parents and guidance should give their female children education and stop the imposition of early marriage on them, and society should encourage girl-child education by awarding a scholarship to them..

KEYWORDS: Girl Child, Education Community Development and Essien Udim

INTRODUCTION

Education is important for everyone but is especially significant for girls and women. This is true not only because education is an entry point to other opportunities, but also because the educational achievements of a woman can have ripple effects within the family and across generations. (Akinola, 2012). Harbison (1973) argued that human resources constitute the ultimate basis for a wealth of nations. Capital and natural resources are passive factors of

production but human beings are the agents who accumulate capital, explore its natural resources, build social economic and political organization, and carry forward and national development. A country which is unable to develop the skills and knowledge of its people, especially those of the girl-child and utilized them effectively in the national economy will be unable to develop anything else.

Investing in girl's education is one of the most effective ways to reduce poverty. Investment in university education for girls yields especially high dividends. Akinola (2013) argues that the girl-child's right to education is an economic, social and cultural right as well as a civil and political right since people cannot fully realise their freedom without education. Like all human rights, the context of the girl child's right to education can be found in both local and international legislative commitments/conventions. Despite all these, the girl-child is still looked at as an object of sex and slavery.

In Nigeria today, many communities deny their women the needed knowledge of Western education which is one of the weapons used to protect her family and her entire household, especially in the northern part of Nigeria where the girl-child is given out to marriage at a very tender age exposing her to different types of reproductive system related diseases, such as vesicovaginal fistula (VVF). In the southern part especially in Anaang land, the girl-child is given out as house help, babysitters and also hawk wares on the streets, while her male counterparts are in school. There is a popular saying that "when one educates a man, one educates a person but when one educates a woman, one educates a nation". This is because the socialization of an individual into any social system or organization starts in childhood, thus the level of the girl child's education plays an important part in this process. A family grows and develops according to the mother's level of education. This show the importance of the girl child which is the gap this work want to fill within the Annang people of Essien Udim Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Harbison and Myer (1971) argued that education is the key that unlocks the door to modernization, while Emile Durkheim stated that education is an instrument through which society perpetuates itself. In Essien Udim Local Government Area, many girls of secondary school ages (13-18 years old) are not in school. They sit in groups setting and resetting their hair, playing Ludo, gossiping, idling all day, etc. despite the free education programme by the state government from primary to secondary education. In Ikpe Anaang and other communities of Essien Udim Local Government Area, most – working class ladies or female civil servants do not live within the communities, but in neighbouring urban centres like Ikot Ekpene, Uyo, Abak, etc. the female teachers in the secondary schools, the nurses of the general hospital and those of the community health centre come from outside the communities. Thus, there are very few or no educated female workers in the study area for the girl-child to emulate or be attracted to. Idleness breeds immorality and as such, these girls become mothers at a very tender age when they are supposed to be in school.

Lack of educational advancement; subsequently put them into joblessness and apprenticeship in the informal economic sector as a hair stylist, seamstress, salesmanship etc. Some go into petty trading, while others engage in Piassava (Idut) processing which is used in climbing rope production, a trade they practised to very old age. It is also very common to see boys idling away, smoking and drinking around during school hours. They have a keen interest

in masquerading around the community when its season comes and other delinquent activities because their illiterate mother's backgrounds impede proper socialization.

Richardson (2009) argues that no community will remain underdeveloped if it has the required human capital. The best instrument for developing any society is to invest in human capital, this is because the required knowledge and skills will guarantee the economic and social liberation of the individual and by implication enhance their contributions to community and national development. Essentially, girls must be educated in terms of their roles in society as producers or reproducers. They are mainly responsible for the care and well-being of their families, they play important roles as educators of future generations, and they perform economic and social functions (Ballara, 2002). Thus for any society to develop, the girl-child must be allowed access to good and qualitative education. This study, therefore, examined the impact of girl-child education on community development with a focus on Essien Udim Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

The following hypothesis were adopted for the study based on the specific objectives of the study;

- H₀: there is a no significant relationship between Girl-Child's education and Community Development
- H₀: there is a significant relationship between Girl-Child's education and women's participation in politics,

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Girl Child's Education and Community Growth

According to Ottaway (2000), the Girl-Child's Education also has a bearing on the economic well-being of our community and the country at large, with education, in adulthood the girl-child could easily gain employment in the formal labour force and therefore contribute not only to her family income but the gross national product, Isaac (2011) asserts that higher education enables girls to provide financial support to their families especially now that the economic recession has made it impossible for a man to provide adequately for his family with his meagre income. The importance of the girl child's education cannot be over-emphasized in any society, since the girl-child constitutes more than half of the population in most societies, their education is vital to any sustainable development. Education is the key that unlocks the door to modernization while Durkheim (1947) argued that education is an instrument through which the society perpetuates itself. It is one of the powerful human institutions that shapes and influences man, society and the environment.

UNICEF (2004) as quoted in Isari (2010), noted that a girl child's education is one of the most important investments that could be used for the future of any country, it could make an enormous difference to a woman's chances of gaining well-paid work and raising a healthy family. Nazi (2015) noted that then Lieutenant Valentine Tereshkova a Russian Air Force Officer in 1963 orbited the earth forty-eight (48) times making 1,200,000 miles in 70 hours 50 minutes from June 16-19. She was the first woman in space, a record no other human being had ever had before then. She becomes the symbol of women the world over.

Mbene (2011) argues that investing in girls' education leads directly to better reproductive health, improved family health, and economic growth for the family and the

community. Newswatch (Feb: 15 2010) described Dr. Dora Akunyili as “Amazon”, the then Director General of NAFDAC who cleaned Nigeria of not only fake drugs but also all fake and substandard consumable products. Dr. Nozi Okonjo-Iweala of Nigeria is the Director of the World Trade Organization (WTO), she is the heroine of Nigeria's debt forgiveness. Salawu (1989) observed that through education, women come to know their rights and they will be able to contribute their quota to the development of society.

Marshal (2003) states that women make up more than half of any nation's population and they have been known to have contributed in many ways to the development of the society. Hence for the girl-child to face the challenges of her time, they require full participation and access to the benefits of formal and informal education and that is the only way the girl-child can contribute maximally to the socio-economic development of their community and Nigeria. Amaka (2014) observes that broad base education of good quality is among the most powerful instruments known to reduce poverty and inequality. With proven benefits for personal health, it also strengthens a nation's economic health by laying the foundation for sustainable economic growth, for individuals and nations. Human Development Report (HDR) (1995) reports that 70% of the world's poor are women. This staggering revelation leads to the conclusion by the HDR that poverty has women's faces. Amaka (2014) argues that a mother's education is a significant variable affecting children's education attainment and opportunities. A mother with a few years of formal education is considerably more likely to send her children to school. In many countries, each additional year of formal education completed by a mother translates into her children remaining in school for an additional one-third to one-half year. The Girl-child's education is very important for it also brings her into the limelight of their society. In Akwa Ibom State and Nigeria, notable women have contributed to the development and in places of authority and there is no administrative post in the World today that women lack behind.

Girls-Child Education and Women Participation in Politics

The girl-child is a female offspring from birth to seventeen years (0-17 years). From eighteen years and above she is regarded as an adult, a woman. As a full-grown woman, she is expected to fully participate and contribute to all activities of the community. Nwala (1985:242) argued that education whether formal or informal is the recognized method whereby a person acquires most of the ideas, beliefs, knowledge, skills and manners necessary not only to combat the hazards and problems of life (physically, theoretically and psychologically) and to secure the needs of life (biological, social and economical) but also to fit into the company of his fellow human beings.

Closky (1979) argued that political participation is those voluntary activities by which members of a society share in the selection of rulers and directly or indirectly in the form of public policy. Nnonyelu (2011) observes that female participation in politics has been peripheral. This is in large measure, due to one's access to education and several important social characteristics, some of which are income, social class, length of stable residence or socio-economic position. The low level of female participation in politics or the near exclusion of females from the political process, is a function of the denial of women's education and all its prerequisites Hartman (1979) opines that human beings are born male and female sexes, but they are created man and woman. Thus, sex is socially constructed and gender roles are therefore assigned to men and women. For instance:- the sex roles which women can perform

by their biology are breastfeeding and giving birth to babies while the gender roles of men which include:- owners of the property, decision making, political issues and headship of households are socially, historically and culturally constructed and have nothing whatsoever to do with a sociological difference (Igbuzor 1999:16). Nnonyehu (2011) Perez de Cuellar (1991) observed that, despite the large turnout of women during elections or a large number of female voters, most women still lag far behind men in power, income and other opportunities. Men have continued to use their advantages to distribute the scarce resources of society to the exclusion of the female gender. Agwomba (1996) argues that women are not economically viable, and do not have the financial wherewithal to compete favourably with their male counterparts in politics. Okoye (2002) noted that many women have the right credentials and indeed all it takes to succeed in politics, but unfortunately, lack the funds to pursue a serious political agenda. Alapiki (2010) maintained that across the world where women play key roles in public office have shown that women in politics and decision-making contribute to redefining political priorities, placing new items on the political agenda that reflect and address concerns as well as providing new perspectives on mainstream political issues. He also argues that women if given the political space will bring to bear their unique perspective.

When women achieve an equal share of political power many things besides politics will change profoundly, breaking down of barriers that constrain the development of individual talents and restrict the range of human resources available to meet society's need will take place". Alapiki (2010:77) observes that participation in politics cannot be separated from other important aspects of women's lives such as marriage, family and employment, thus an understanding of the success of women in political participation as well as the barriers women face in reaching equal participation requires a fuller appreciation of the context within which men live. Shaul (1982) observes that in a few countries where women held important national office, such women have often come from upper-class families with a history of political participation and high education.

Alapki (2010) argues that political participation includes not only the right to vote and actual voting behaviour but also the candidacy, election and appointment of women to all levels of government and within the party structure. It may also include women's participation in grassroots organizations such as neighbourhood groups among others. Shaul (1982) observes that societal attitudes which value women principally as mothers and wives pose a major obstacle to women's participation in politics and other important life activities. The societal attitudes which are embodied in all cultures in different degrees, constitute the major barriers to women's political participation.

Durkheim (1947) believes that educational change is not only an important reflection of the underlying structural and cultural changes but also an agent in that process. Thus no analysis of stability and change in any given society or community could be completed without a careful examination of its education system. Alapiki (2010:182) argues that by tradition and culture, the woman in Nigeria is expected to play second fiddle and take low-status jobs, she is excluded from positions of authority; that woman is not supposed to sit in the shrine the very place village holders meet to take vital decisions on community affairs. There are female generals in the Nigerian Armed Forces and the Para Military Sector, there are Females as captains of industries and Chief Executive Officers in the economic sector in Nigeria and the world over.

Gidden (1993) noted that Golda Meir of Israel, Indira Gandhi and Margaret Thatcher of

Great Britain were powerful Heads of State. Helen Johnson Sirleaf, Catherine Samba Panza, Sara Kuganelwa, Luisa Dias Diogo, and Joyce Mujuru had been President and Head of Government in their council, Liberia, Central African Republic, Namibia, Zimbabwe and Mozambique respectively. Condoleezza Rice was the most influential woman on earth during President Bush's administration in the United States of America. There is Nkosazana Dlamini – Zuma the Chairperson of the Commission of the African Union. Nnonyelu (2009) argued that aside from such women like Margaret Ekpo, Mrs Udo Udoma, Mrs Kuti, Janet Akirinade, Janet Mokelu, Oyibo Odinamadu other notable women personalities include Franca Afegbua, Florence Ita-Giwa, Kairat Gwadebe and Stella Omu. In recent times we also cited Helen Esuen, Ikwo Inyang, Chris Anyawu, Oluremi Tinubu, Monsurat Sunmonu, and Stella Oduah Dr Glory Edet has also been an influential Politician in Akwa Ibom State. In Nigeria women have shown considerable interest in political representation including Sarah Jibril of Kogi who vied for the Presidency in the 2023 election, Patricia Ette was the first female Senate President in 2015. There are girls and women as counsellors, Local Government Chairmen, State House of Assembly members, Members of the House of Representatives and Senators.

Socio-Cultural Factors and Low Level Of Girl-Child Enrolment in Schools

Murzi (2003) argues that in Nigeria the educational participation of the girl-child is notably lower than that of boys, gender has continued to play a major role in determining school attendance, performance and progress. Being a female is negatively associated with enrolment, attainment and performance. Throughout history, the world has witnessed the transfer of women like property from fathers to husbands to fulfil socially determined roles and in most societies, women are often not allowed to hold or inherit property.

Alapiki (2010:179) noted that numerous societies have cultural restrictions that keep women subordinate, there exist some ways of restricting women from attaining equal status with men in all spheres of life. Apart from the spread of discrimination against women, some cultural factors had contributed in no small measure to the lack of interest in public life on the part of women. Mandell (1981) noted that societal attitudes had been reinforced by most religious doctrines and structures, these doctrines place women in a secondary position to men. Some religions require the separation of men and women at religious services. Women in Development (1995) observes that there are still cultures and religions that see women as chattels who should neither be seen nor heard. Widows are still victims of barbaric customs that punish women for the death of their husbands. That in certain claims women have been oppressed for so long that many of them cannot imagine or appreciate the possibility of life without those culturally sanctioned shackles.

Olamukoro and Ominunu (2011) observed that the Nigerian constitution (1999) guarantees equality of education for all its citizens, regardless of religion, ethnic origin, circumstances of birth and above all sex. However, various socio-cultural and religious practices such as preference for a male child, early marriage and “Purdah” have gone a long way to prevent the Nigerian girl-child from exercising their legal rights to equal education of the girl-child in Nigeria. These Practices include:- cultural inhibition, erroneous interpretation of religious injunctions, early betrothal of girls in marriage, gender insensitive educational environments, curricula and teaching, methods, lack of encouragement from the wider society, over overburdening of the girl-child with household core and labour. Osokaya (2005) cited in Olamukoro and Oniunu (2011) reports that about 30% of Nigerian teenagers who drop out of

school have already begun childbearing before the age of 18. Umar and Gbana (2004) state that in Nigeria, women are expected to play second fiddle and take up low-status jobs. They traditionally have been debased and dishonoured by the fact that they are supposed to consider motherhood as the principal purpose of their existence. Voorhees (1973) observed that women were forbidden to own property, to engage in politics, to pursue education or to engage in virtually any activity outside the walls of their home. In many traditional societies, women were legal minors and dependent wards of men. Umar and Gbana (2004) argued that in many families, the education of the girl-child is not perceived as important. Some view it as a waste because as the girl-child grows up and gets married the money spent on her education is never fully recovered from her bride price. Some parents are unwilling to send the girl-child to school even when they have the means to educate her, ignorance and illiteracy of parents account greatly for the negligence of the girl-child's education. They find no reason why the girl-child should be given equal rights with the boy-child. In a situation where the parents are poor, they would always prefer to use the title resources to send the boy-child to school and allow the girl-child to either hawk or engage in other activities (Isaac 2011).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Several Theories have been employed to explain research in girl-child education and community development in the course of this present investigation; the following theoretical expositions have been applied.

Functionalism

Functionalists maintained that after primary socialization within the family, the school takes over as the focal socializing agency. School acts as a bridge between the family and society as a whole, preparing children for their adult roles. Within the family, the child is judged and treated largely in terms of particularistic standards. Parents treat the child as their particular child rather than judging her or him in terms of standards or yardsticks that can be applied to every individual. However, in the wider society, the individual is treated and judged in terms of universalistic standards which are applied to all members of the society.

Within the family the child's status is ascribed, it is fixed by birth. However, in advanced industrial society, status in adult life is largely achieved, for example, individuals achieve their occupational status. Thus the child must move from the particularistic standard and ascribed status of the family to universalistic standards and achieve the status of an adult in society. The school prepares young people for transition. It establishes universalistic standards in terms of which all pupils achieve their status. Their conduct is assessed against the yardstick of the school rules. Their achievement is measured by performance in examinations. The same standards are applied to all students regardless of ascribed characteristics such as sex, race, family background or class of origin, schools operate on meritocratic principles. Status is achieved based on merit, (Parsons 1961).

As such the girl-child must be given equal education to enable her to attain universalistic standards.

Social Learning Theory

Social Learning theory is a learning process and social behaviour which proposes that new behaviour can be acquired by observing imitating and modelling by Albert Bandura in 1971. It stated that learning is a cognitive process that takes place in a social context and can occur purely through observation or direct instruction even in the absence of motor

reproduction or direct reinforcement. In addition to the observation of behaviour learning also occurs through observation of rewards and punishments a process known as vicarious reinforcement. When a particular is rewarded regularly, it will most likely persist (Bandura 1963).

METHODOLOGY

This study was carried out in the seven main communities of Essien Udim Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State of Nigeria. Essien Udim Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State is an amalgamation of Essien Annang Local Government Area and Udim Local Government Area when what is Akwa Ibom State now was a Mainland part of Cross River State. This means that it is made up of two separate Local Government Areas of Cross River State until the creation of Akwa Ibom State on the 23rd of September 1987. Essien Udim Local Government Area is the biggest Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State. She has a common boundary with Abia State on the North and West, on the East with Ikot Ekpene, South – East with Ikono, and the South with Abak, Etim Ekpo and Ika Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. The systematic random sampling technique was adopted in the selection of respondents. Two main categories of people were selected purposefully and these were the village Heads and the women opinion leaders of Essien Udim Local Government Communities. There are seven (7) clans or communities in Essien Udim Local Government Area, each with several villages. For instance, Ikpe Annang has 14 villages, Ukana (28) villages. Other clans Adiasim 12, Odoro Ikot 17, Ekpenyong, 26, Okon 18, and Afaha 10 villages.

The Two village heads and two women opinion leaders were purposefully selected from each of the seven communities making 14 each of these categories. The other categories were young Girls 4, 4 young boys, then 10 men and 10 women systematically sampled after every 5 houses in the seven (7) communities making, 14 village Heads, 14 women opinion leaders, 28 young Girls, 28 young boys, 70 women and 70 men. A total of 224 respondents were sampled for this study. The instrument used in this study was a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire technique was chosen because it makes it possible to cover a large number of people spread over a large area. It is also economical in terms of money, time and energy. According to Akpan (2001), the questionnaire introduced the art of formality and documentary evidence in support of findings and the structured questionnaire was drawn and used for obtaining information from the respondents. Statistical tools used for analysis in this study were a combination of simple percentage (X^0) and the chi-square (X^2) tool of analysis.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Analysis of hypothesis I: The impact of Girl-Child's education on community development. The responses of the respondents show that Girl-Child education has an impact on community development e.g the women opinion leaders noted that the development of any community depends solely on the educational background of the women who socialise their children, while the men argued that educated women make sure that all their children are educated. This revelation supports – OchOcho's(2005) argument that education made the girl-child a functional member of society for transformation and development. Marshal (2003) asserted that women make up more than half of the Nigerian population and they have been known to contribute in many ways to the development of the society.

Analysis of hypothesis question II: Is there any significant relationship between Girl-Child Education and Women's participation in politics? The responses revealed that education-influenced women sampled cited female senators in Nigeria from the first republic to this 8th assembly of the Nigerian Senate where Senator Mrs Helen Esuene is a member, that Gloria Useh was the immediate past Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area Council Chairman. The village heads and other men cited different achievements courtesy of female politicians. These findings support Alapiki's (2010) argument that women play roles in public office and that women in politics and decision-making contribute to redefining political priorities and placing new items on mainstream political issues. Shaul (1982) asserted that the rising number of women in politics indicates that human beings are making progress toward a more human world, not that women are necessarily more human than men but any society that categorically excludes half its rules itself will be ruled in a way that is less than human.

The analysis of whether socio-cultural factors account for low levels of Girl-Child enrolment in schools, shows that apart from a few respondents who complain about girls' promiscuous lifestyle that lead to unwanted pregnancy thereby keeping them out of school, the majority 89% of the respondents blamed sociocultural factors such as early betrothal, male child preference and so on as the main factors that account for low-level Girl-Child enrolment in schools. This analysis supports Nwosu's (1999) argument that various socio-cultural practices such as preference for the male child, and early marriage and soon have gone a long way to prevent the Nigerian Girl-Child from exercising her legal right to equal education to the fullest. Therefore leads to a low level of girl-child enrolment in schools, Gidado as reported in Umar and Gbana (2004) argued that despite the various programs put in place by the governments to promote girl-child education, it is disheartening to not that disparity in access to education is still in favour of the male by some families.

CONCLUSION

This research work has examined the impact of Girl child education on community development in Essien Udim Local Government of Akwa Ibom State. The Girl child has been discussed by many others. The researcher makes an introductory remarks on Girl-Child's education and its rationalities as well as refining the reward of Girl-child to the community according to different scholars. The research also explores how the Girl-child has often been denied her right through medieval beliefs. A lot of literature has been reviewed according to objectives from books, journalists and magazines on the impact of girl-child education on community development. The methodology employed in carrying out the research was a survey. The studies reveal that many families still preference the male child in terms of education, betrothal marriages are still being practised in some communities in Essien Udim Local Government Area, and some families prefer men to engage fully in politics but not women.

With increasing access to education especially as the free and compulsory education policy is still in force and other opportunities to the Girl-child, it is hoped that female involvement in community development, participation in politics and government shall be on the increase. Doing away with medieval socio-cultural practices in this 21st Century for old discrimination against women is unacceptable. Sustainable progress or development cannot come about when half of any nation's population is excluded from the political process for reasons bothering the mundane Globalization of the world makes it doubly imperative that

equal access irrespective of sex and gender is a sure way of getting Essien Udim Local Government Area in particular, Akwa Ibom State and Nigeria in general out of the wood.

The whole world had witnessed that the 1st human being to orbit the Planet Earth 48 times in Three Days being in the air for 70 hours 50 minutes from 16 June to 19 June 1963 was a woman LT. Valentina Tereshkora, Ngozi Okonjo Iweala today is the Director of the World Trade Centre in New York. The stability of the nation is not guaranteed when Nigeria is standing on one limb. The Country can do better if all hand hands (both male and female) are on deck.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In light of the findings, the following are recommended:

1. The society should forward both boys and girls in the provision of education.
2. Parents and guidance should as a matter of honesty stop the imposition of early child marriage on the Girl-child.
3. Essien Udim Local Government Authority should mount a campaign and encourage its citizens to do away with mundane sociocultural and traditional practices that derogate women.
4. Government should make it mandatory for Civil servants serving in hospitals and health centres, in secondary schools and in Local Government offices to take accommodation in such areas.

REFERENCES

- 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2011) Educational Objective, Chapter 2 section 18 (1)
- Akinola The(2012) the Gils-Child and Education in Nigeria Leadership Newspaper Group
- Akpan, E. (2004) Principles of Research and Statistics. An Introductory Approach, Calabar Executive Publishers.
- Alapiki, H. (2010) Politics and Governance in Nigeria. Port Harcourt, Shape Publisher. Nigeria
- Ballara, M. (2002) Girls and Women Literacy: Women and Development Series. London, Zed Books Limited.
- Durkheim E. (1947) Division of Labour in Society, New York Free Press.
- Egbo J. and Manna, (2011) Promotion Women Education for National Development Journal of Women in Colleges of Education (ESCET - JOWICE) Maiden Edition pp.109-114
- Gidden A. (1993) Sociology, Cambridge Polity Press
- Gistereaa (2013) Girl-child Education – Challenges Faced in the Society. Retrieved Thursday 5 2013.
- Habisond and Myeric (1971) “Quantitative Indication of Human Research Development in Education” In Gez (ed) Comparative and International Perspective. New York. Holt Rinehart and Winston Inc.
- Harbison, F. (1973) Human Resources as the Wealth of Nation. New York, Oxford University Press.
- Hartman H. (1979) “The Unhappy Marriage of Marxism and Feminism towards a more

- progressive Union” The second wave: A Reader in Feminist Theory. New York, Routledge.
- Human Development Report (1995) NUDP
- Igbuzor, O. (1999) Methodology Issues in Gender Studies in Nigeria. Nigeria Social Scientist pp 14-20
- Jibril (2014) Communication for development
Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences, Rome – Italy MCSER Publishing.
- Marshall, N. (2003) Gender Equity in Early Childhood Education. In a word of Difference. Reading on Teaching Young Children in a Diverse Society. Washington DC, New York.
- Mbene J. (2011) The Importance of Educating a Girl-child, retrieved Thursday 5 2015.
- Murzi (2023) in Olomukoro and Omiunu (2011)
Strategies for Expanding Access Education for the Girl-child.d
National Population Commission (2006) National Census.
- Newswatch (Feb 15 2010) The Akunyili Revolt, Oregon – Lagos Newswatch Communication Limited.
- Newswatch (Sept r5 2011) Judiciary in Disarray the New Economic Blue Print pp. 45. Oregon – Lagos, Newswatch communication Limited.
- Nnabuife N. (2000) Education and Functionality: A moment from Reflection” Paper presented at the 2nd Conference of the National Association for the Advancement of Knowledge 21st June Nsugbe Nwafor Orizu College of Education.
- Nwala, T. (1985) Igbo Philosophy, Lagos – Nigeria, Lantern Books.
- Nwosu, O. (1999) The African Women: Nigeria Perspective: Lagos: Bima Publications.
- Ocho, O. (2005) Cultured and Girl-child Education. Conference of Women in Colleges of Education, Ministry of Education Publication Kaduna – Nigeria.
- Offiong, D. (2013) Globalization and Africa (Reverse Robin Hoodism) Ipaja- Lagos Nigeria, APEXD Books Limited.
- Okodye I. (2000) Issues and Strategies